

SUPPLEMENT E: CLUSTER ASSIGNMENTS FOR THE DENDROGRAM IN FIGURE 4

The file `cluster-assignments.tsv` contains the cluster assignments from 6 different cuts of the dendrogram in Figure 4. The column labels in the file are defined as follows:

<code>label</code>	drug-gene pair
<code>cluster</code>	cluster assignment for cut height 0.55
<code>id</code>	tip ID for the drug-gene pair (no relationship to IDs in other supplements)
<code>c0.4</code>	cluster assignment for cut height 0.4
<code>c0.3</code>	cluster assignment for cut height 0.3
<code>c0.25</code>	cluster assignment for cut height 0.25
<code>c0.1</code>	cluster assignment for cut height 0.1
<code>c0.05</code>	cluster assignment for cut height 0.05
<code>cluster.ordered</code>	cluster assignment for cut height 0.55, corresponding to label in Figure 5
<code>count</code>	number of times drug-gene pair in label are co-mentioned in sentences
<code>pgkb</code>	binary: 1 if known PGx association, 0 if not
<code>drugbank</code>	binary: 1 if known drug-target association, 0 if not
<code>drug</code>	the name of the drug from the drug-gene pair
<code>gene</code>	the name of the gene from the drug-gene pair